

LANGUAGE, NATURE AND HUMAN RESPONSIBILITY: RESTRUCTURING THE ENVIRONMENTAL ETHICS IN RICHARD POWERS' THE OVERSTORY

Zoobia Abbas^{*1}, Mamona Yasmeen Khan²

^{*1}PhD Scholar: Department of English, The Women University Multan, Punjab, Pakistan,
Humanities Department, COMSATS University Islamabad, Vehari Campus, Punjab, Pakistan-61100

²Professor, Chairperson English Department, The Women University Multan

Corresponding Author: * ¹zoobia@cuivehari.edu.pk

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated the role of language in restructuring the environmental ethics in society through highlighting the ecological themes in fictions particularly in Richard Power's *The Overstory*. The research examined the art of employing certain linguistic devices like metaphor and symbolism in literature to highlight the complex bond present between language, nature, and human responsibility. The characters in the novel are set to challenge ethical problems linked to deforestation, conservation, and the inherent value of the natural world, with their decisions deeply influenced by the language and narratives they construct. The study employed Arran Stubbe's theory to critically analyse the eco linguistic aspects in *The Overstory* promoting the language of environmental activism. Certain ethical inferences of human interaction with nature, including issues like deforestation and conservation are highlighted and analysed through characters' use of language to advocate for ecological preservation and to foster a deeper connection to the environment. The research revealed that *The Overstory* not only develops readers understanding of eco-linguistic discourse but also challenged to reexamine their ethical responsibilities toward nature. The findings of the research emphasized the significant role that literature and language play in shaping environmental consciousness and contributing to insights in the broader social attitudes toward nature that the novel reflects.

Keywords: Language, Nature, Eco-linguistics, environmental ethics, Ecology, symbols, Human responsibility

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the Study: Ecology, Language, and Human Beings

Due to persistent environmental issues and human perception of the ecology around them made it a necessity to explore human action in the world as significant or otherwise. For this purpose, it is significant to probe the role of literature in bringing knowledge to everyday mind through the use of certain linguistic devices. Literature plays a crucial role in bridging the connection between literature itself, ecology and ethics as it shapes trans-temporal and trans-cultural behaviors

(Löschnigg, 2019). To explore such behaviors, ecolinguistics is pivotal as this branch of linguistics explores the relationship between language and the environment by identifying certain perspectives in language to shaping human perceptions of nature. *The Overstory* written by Powers provides a rich tapestry of language that intricately weaves together narratives of individuals deeply connected with trees and forests with a purpose to bring environmental awareness and the consequences of human actions towards them (Clarke, 2022). The present

study is conducted to understand and bring forth to its reader the contemporary issues, human beings are facing such as deforestation, unethical and nonserious behavior towards environment. The purpose is to identify and interpret the behavior towards contemporary environmental issues. The overstory served the purpose to examine the ethical dilemmas through its characters against environmental degradation by exploring through language certain ethical perspectives that challenge the minds and bring awareness towards certain issues regarding deforestation, conservation, and interconnectedness of human beings with the nature.

Powers' narrative explored the profound interconnectedness between language, nature, and human responsibility. The novel is rich in the use of linguistic devices like symbols and metaphors as well as terminologies related to environmental sciences that made the trees and forests an entity with voices having the capacity to serve as an agent of vocalizing human responsibility towards nature. The trees were shown with their capacity of storytelling and the linguistic strategy used in this context blurs conventional boundaries between human and non-human communication. It challenged the readers to reexamine their association with environment and to acknowledge nature's inherent ability to communicate. Present research is focused on the analysis of eco-linguistic elements and the message the elements conveyed ethical awareness present in the selected novel. The narrative discusses a range of researches in the field of linguistics to unfold the linguistics choices that Powers used to highlight ethical dilemmas and responsibilities of human beings towards nature. The characters are portrayed to confront choices related to deforestation, conservation, and the fundamental value of the natural world. The research question is focused on how Powers employed the linguistic terms within the narrative of *The Overstory* to address the environmental issues and individual actions. The research pointed out the ways the characters were depicted to involve in making ethical decisions through the deployment of certain linguistic terms within the novel. Through textual analysis of the selected novel, it is observed and described how different linguistic patterns are utilized to represent the language of environmental activism and advocated for tree conservation to promote a

deeper connection to environment. Hence, the present work explained the significant role of literature and storytelling in determining environmental consciousness and rousing ecological stewardship. Being limited to the field of eco-linguistics, linguistic choices and metaphoric language in the novel are explored to identify the individuals' relationships with its environment.

The study is a fictional representation about environmental knowledge and significantly highlighted that linguistic choices are not only contributory to the comprehension of the eco-literary qualities of the text but also enhance readers' understanding of ecology, human responsibility and specifically eco-linguistic discourse. The complicated relations between language, nature, and human responsibility in Powers' work is elaborated and served the purpose of the research to explain the novel's influence on readers' environmental ethics and its reflection of broader social attitudes towards nature. This exploration serves as a valuable contribution to the understanding of environmental themes and moral inquiries embedded in "The Overstory." The study by examining the intricate connections between ecology, language, and human beings highlighted the thoughtful chemistry present between these elements; it is accentuating the significance of language in shaping perceptions and awareness towards nature. The narrative in *The Overstory* is a rich context for the exploration of eco-linguistic elements and reconsidering ethical dimensions. It outlined Powers' use of language, as a key tool in endowing trees and the forest with voices and agency. The background underscored the novel's role as a rich tapestry that challenged the conventional boundaries between human and non-human communication.

1.2. OBJECTIVES

1. To explore the ethical dilemmas portrayed in novels in the context of deforestation, conservation, and their evolving relationship with the environment.
2. To examine the role of language in shaping the ethical perspectives on environmental issues.
3. To explore the role of English narrations in utilizing language to effectively convey ecological themes.

1.3. RESEARCH QUESTION

- How does Richard Powers' novel *The Overstory* employ language and narrative techniques to inspire environmental consciousness and to promote ethical stewardship among readers?

2. Methodology

The research is a qualitative analysis that focuses on the novel *The Overstory* as the primary text. The novel is rich in narrative techniques and is fitting most to explore ecolinguistics elements and environmental ethical dimension as the major theme to explore. The researcher has focused on linguistic analysis for the exploration of the text. For extracting linguistic elements, the focus of attention is on the symbols, metaphors, and environmental terminologies used in the novel with the purpose of considering the contribution made by linguistic choices to the novel's eco-literary qualities. For exploring the theme of environmental ethics, the characters and narrative structure were analyzed with their involvement in discussions related to deforestation, conservation, and the intrinsic value of nature. In the end, a major comparison across characters was made to explore the contrast of language to identify the patterns and variations that serve the purpose of ethical consideration.

3. Theoretical Framework

Stibbe in *Ecolinguistics: Language, Ecology, and the Stories We Live By*, plans eight types of ecolinguistics analysis, that the researcher is using as a framework to study language's role in the novel *The Overstory*. These eight types are utilized to understand the environmental issues, particularly

1. **Ideologies:** Ideologies are underlying beliefs and values in language. they shape how people think about the environment.
2. **Framing:** framing is the way language borders ecological issues, either as problems or opportunities.
3. **Metaphors:** Figurative language that influences the way human beings conceptualize nature. for example, the way they see nature as a machine or as a community of living beings.
4. **Evaluations:** The judgements either positive or negative about ecology as embedded in language. For example: describing nature as "wild" or "pristine".

5. **Identities:** The art of constructing the identity of humans and other species. For example, human exceptionalism vs. ecological kinship.

6. **Convictions:** There are certain ethical beliefs expressed through language in the form of ideas about what is right or wrong in relation to the environment.

7. **Erasure:** when certain ecological realities or voices in discourse are omitted or marginalized, the process of such analysis is called erasure.

8. **Salience:** The use of prominent, backgrounded and ignored elements in discourse.

4. Eco-Linguistic Elements and Ethical Dimensions in "The Overstory"

4.1. Strategic use of Environmental Terminologies

The strategic use of environmental terminologies in *The Overstory* emerges as a crucial aspect of the novel's eco-linguistic narrative. Powers uses these terms not only to convey ecological concepts but also to weave a linguistic tapestry that reflects characters' ethical dilemmas, evolving relationships with nature, and the symbolic power of language. Analyzing these environmental terms offers insights into the deep intersection of language, nature, and human responsibility within the novel. *The Overstory* is a poignant exploration of the profound connection between humans and the natural world, particularly trees. Throughout the novel, Powers employed a rich array of environmental terminology to depict intricate ecosystems, diverse flora and fauna, and the enduring significance of trees in the face of human-induced environmental degradation. For example, the title *The Overstory* itself is too symbolic to relate the entire story with deforestation. In Environmental sciences, the word 'overstory' stands for the highest layer of a forest canopy, composed of the tallest trees. The overstory trees provide shade and shelter for the understory plants and animals below, and they play an important role in regulating the forest's climate and nutrient cycling. The title is significant as it deals with the novel's entire theme of interconnectedness, resilience, and relationship between humans and nature.

"You live between three trees. One is behind you. The Lote-the tree of life.... Another tree stands in front of you-Fusang. A magical mulberry tree far to the east, where they keep the elixir of life....." "The third tree is all

around you: Now. And like Now itself, it will follow wherever you go... (p. 33)

The novel depicts the intricate ecosystem of forests. It highlighted the various species like.....with a delicate balance of life. The use of terms like "riparian corridors" (117), "old-growth forests," (240) and "understory" (339), and "(bio) diversity" (275) to illustrate the complex web of life that thrives within these vital ecosystems.

"They're an ecosystem unto themselves, hosting more than a thousand species of invertebrates. Framer of cities, king of industrial trees, that tree without which America would have been a very different proposition". (p. 146)

Powers has investigated the biology and physiology of trees, providing a deeper understanding of their remarkable resilience and adaptability. Terms like "sapwood"(95), "heartwood"(342) "phloem and xylem" (413), and "photosynthesis" are used to explain the intricate mechanisms that allow trees to reach astounding heights, endure harsh conditions, and play a crucial role in carbon sequestration. There is also a detailed delineation of the impact of human forestry practices on forest ecosystems. Terms like "selective logging," "clear-cutting," and "deforestation" are used to highlight the harmful effects of unsustainable practices on biodiversity and forest health. *The Overstory* brings into consideration the environmental threats that the Powers raises awareness of the pressing environmental worldwide threats like deforestation, climate change, and invasive species. Terms like "habitat destruction," "global warming," and "endangered species" underscore the urgency of conservation efforts to protect these vital ecosystems.

"Aspens everywhere, and it boggles her mind that not one of them has grown from seed. All through this part of the West, few aspens have done so in ten thousand years". (p. 137)

5. Environmental Ethics and Advocacy

The novel interweaves the stories of individuals who dedicate their lives to protecting trees and the environment. Terms like "environmental activism," "ecofeminism," and "sustainable practices" highlight the diverse approaches and motivations of those who fight for the preservation of natural systems. Powers emphasizes the interconnectedness of all living things, using terms like "ecosystem services" and

"web of nature" to illustrate the profound impact that trees have on human well-being and the overall health of the planet. For example, in the novel Powers writes:

"Love is a tree with branches in forever with roots in eternity and a trunk nowhere at all". (364)

He also writes:

"Not more plants, boss. You can't make a game out of plants. Unless you give them bazookas". (p. 393)

The novel explores the profound symbolism and cultural significance of trees throughout history and across different societies. For example, in the novel there is a description:

"Olivia pans the camera around the transformed grove. Where there had been measurements and prospects, a project of hard numbers, there are now only skippers and swallowtails, morphos, hairstreaks, and heaths. It could be a grove of sacred firs in the Mexican mountains....." (p. 250)

Terms like "sacred threads"(89), "Prayer-covered papers"(89), and "folk dances" (414) highlight the deep reverence and connection that humans have long felt for these majestic plants.

Powers demonstrated the power of language and storytelling in raising awareness and inspiring action for environmental protection. He uses evocative imagery, scientific precision, and emotional resonance to convey the importance of trees and the urgent need for their conservation. Consider the following lines, that are illustrative of imagery, scientific precision as well as emotional bounding with trees:

"Men and trees are closer cousins than you think. We're two things hatched from the same seed, heading off in opposite directions, using each other in a shared place. That place needs all its parts." (431)

At another place:

"Trees stand at the heart of ecology, and they must come to stand at the heart of human politics. Tagore said, Trees are the earth's endless effort to speak to the listening heaven. But people-oh, my word-people! People could be the heaven that the Earth is trying to speak to." (431-432)

Both the passages are illustrative of the technique of constructing the identity of humans and environment around as illustrated in Stibbe's theory of ecolinguistics. The kinship present between trees and homo sapience to getting more and more balanced relationship is obvious through the utilization of language in the narrative.

In the same way, the use of environmental terminology served to enrich the narrative as a powerful tool for education and support for environmental ethics. By weaving these terms into the fabric of the story, Powers engaged its readers to comprehend complex environmental issues by fostering a deeper appreciation for the intricate beauty and vital role of trees in our world. The novel framed the trees as protagonist rather mere objects. These trees appeared to raise ethical questions surrounding deforestation and the exploitation of natural resources by confronting the moral implications. The characters in the novels are framed as participating in activities that lead to the destruction of forests, questioning the prioritization of economic gains over environmental stewardship.

"This is not our world with trees in it. It's a world of trees, where humans have just arrived". (404)

The novel shared ethical dimension of conservation through language. The ethical ideas are prominent throughout the narrative. The convention (Stibbe, 2015) is promoted through characters who advocated for the preservation of biodiversity, questioning the consequences of actions like clear-cutting and selective logging. The novel explores the intrinsic value of every species and the importance of maintaining a balanced ecosystem. The novel delves into the ethical complexities of human relationships with trees. Characters grapple with the morality of viewing trees solely as resources for human use versus recognizing them as sentient beings with intrinsic value. The concept of anthropomorphism is explored, challenging traditional hierarchies in which humans hold dominion over nature.

"But people have no idea what time is. They think it's a line, spinning out from three seconds behind them, then vanishing just as fast into the three seconds of fog just ahead. They can't see that time is one spreading ring wrapped around another, outward and outward until the thinnest skin of Now depends for its being on the enormous mass of everything that has already died". (343)

The novel scrutinized the impact of various human practices on forest ecosystems. It highlights the ethical dimensions of activities like clear-cutting, which disrupt the delicate balance of life within forests. The characters confront the ethical consequences of disrupting ecosystems and the subsequent loss of biodiversity.

"People have no corner on curious behavior. Other creatures-bigger, slower, older, more durable: call the shots, make the weather, feed creation, and create the very air". (120)

The cultural and symbolic significance of trees is a recurring ethical theme. The novel explores how different cultures perceive and revere trees, emphasizing the ethical obligation to respect and preserve these cultural symbols. The destruction of sacred groves becomes a focal point for ethical reflection. The narrative invites readers to consider the long-term ethical consequences of human actions on the environment. Characters confront the repercussions of past decisions, reflecting on the impact of historical deforestation and the ethical imperative to address and rectify these consequences.

A central ethical theme in the novel is the interconnectedness of all living things. Characters grapple with the concept of collective responsibility, recognizing that individual actions contribute to a larger environmental narrative. The narrative underscores the ethical imperative for society to collectively address environmental challenges.

"Here's a little outsider information, and you can wait for it to be confirmed. A forest knows things. They wire themselves up underground. There are brains down there, ones our own brains aren't shaped to see. Root plasticity, solving problems and making decisions. Fungal synapses. What else do you want to call it? Link enough trees together, and a forest grows aware." (430)

6. Interpretation and Conclusion

The analysis of environmental terminologies and language through the parameter as proposed by Stibbe (2015) in *The Story we Live by*, expressed that the narrative of *The Overstory* is a meticulous integration of language that purposefully conveyed the ecological concepts and ethical considerations. Power has crafted a profound intersection of language, nature, and human responsibility in a linguistic tapestry where environmental terms were transcended as mere tools; they become vehicles for storytelling, advocacy, and raising awareness about the intricate ecosystems. It is obvious through the analysis that the writer has competently weaved the environmental terminologies, including the titular term "Overstory". The language of the narrative is symbolic carrying multilayered meanings that reflect the interconnectedness,

resilience, and relationship between humans and nature. The writer has skillfully unified scientific precision with emotive terms like "sapwood"(95), "heartwood"(139), and "photosynthesis" (129), providing a comprehensive understanding of tree biology while evoking deep emotional connections. The impact of human forestry practices on forest ecosystems, the deployment of the terms like "selective logging," "clear-cutting," and "deforestation" to emphasize the consequences of unsustainable practices are inventively examined by the novel. The knowledge about global awareness and environmental threats, the description of deforestation and alarming climate change, are vocalized using terms like "habitat destruction," "global warming," and "endangered species". The novel emphasized the urgency of conservation efforts and interweaves stories of environmental activism, ecofeminism, and sustainable practices, by stressing the need of interconnectedness of all living things.

Hence, it is clear that the narrative of *The Overstory* served as a catalyst for cultivating environmental consciousness among readers. The writer weaved environmental terminologies that inspired its readers to explore the complex web of life, developing their understanding of ecosystems, biodiversity, and the profound interconnectedness of nature. The novel acted as a stimulus for the readers to reflect on their ethical stances, particularly when characters were represented as grappled with choices related to deforestation, conservation, and the intrinsic value of the natural world. The study encourages the future researchers to explore and reconsider the narrative for understanding and explaining the consequences of human actions on the environment. It also provides the way for understanding the role of environmental activism and anthropocentrism as an unexplored field in the narrative. *The Overstory* typifies the power of storytelling to shape perspectives, to challenge norms, and to inspire action. The analysis suggests that literature can significantly influence readers' attitudes and foster environmental stewardship through the use of scientific language. The study of eco-linguistic elements and ethical dimensions

in *The Overstory* endorsed a profound insight for readers by shaping their environmental ethics and potentially influencing societal attitudes toward nature. Powers's deliberate use of language serves as a transformative tool, inviting readers to reflect on their relationship with the environment, make ethical decisions, and actively participate in the collective responsibility of preserving the natural world.

"No one sees trees. We see fruit, we see nuts, we see wood, we see shade. We see ornaments or pretty fall foliage. Obstacles blocking the road or wrecking the ski slope. Dark, threatening places that must be cleared. We see branches about to crush our roof. We see a cash crop. But trees - trees are invisible." (403).

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